

BEHAVIOURAL TAXATION AND ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study examines the impact of behavioral taxation on the organisational performance of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria. Drawing on the theory of planned behaviour, the research examines how taxpayers' perceptions of fairness and confidence in government influence their compliance attitudes and, in turn, impact enterprise performance. Using a cross-sectional survey research design from a population of 386,655 registered SMEs in Nigeria, and the sample size of 399 participants was derived using Taro Yamane's formula for a known population using stratified random sampling technique was adopted to ensure adequate representation of different categories of MSMEs. Primary data was collected using structured questionnaires after validity and reliability tests, and secondary data from already existing literature. The responses obtained from the questionnaires administered to the participants were analysed using univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis, and the findings reveal a positive and statistically significant relationship between tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government with organisational performance (growth performance and operational performance). The results suggest that when MSME operators perceive tax processes as fair, equitable, and administered by a trustworthy government, they are more likely to comply voluntarily, resulting in improved operational efficiency and business outcomes. The study underscores the importance of strengthening tax administration, enhancing transparency, and supportive environment for MSME growth in Nigeria.*

Introduction

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) form the backbone of most developing

economies and are recognised as engines of economic growth, innovation, and employment generation (OECD, 2023). In Nigeria, MSMEs

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account for over 90% of all businesses and contribute nearly 50% to the Gross National Product (GDP) and about 80% of total employment (SMEDAN, 2022). Notwithstanding their critical function in the economy, MSMEs in Nigeria continue to suffer from the threat to survival and organisational performance, such as inadequate infrastructure, policy inconsistency, and a burdensome taxation environment (Oloyede et al, 2024; Ildigwe, 2023). Appah and Duoduo (2023a) maintain that MSMEs are the major employer of labour and they play a very strategic influence in the development and growth of the Nigerian economy, but their contribution to sustainable economic growth is minimal. Umukoro and Onou (2024) assert that in Nigeria, SMEs are defined as those entrepreneurial businesses with a small number of employees of between 1-100 for small-sized businesses and up to 500 or more for medium-sized companies (CBN Report, 2020). SMEs in Nigeria are broadly defined as businesses with a turnover of less than 100 million Naira per annum and/or less than 300 employees and having a capital investment not exceeding 2 million (excluding the cost of land) or a minimum of 5million Naira (CBN Report, 2020). The Federal Ministry of Commerce and Industry of Nigeria defines small-scale business as a business with a capital investment of not over 750 thousand Naira. According to Sule (1986) in Umukoro and Onou (2024) a small-scale enterprise has a labor size of 11-100 workers or a total cost of not more than

50 million Naira including working capital but excluding cost of land; while a medium scale enterprise has a labor size of between 101-300 workers or a total cost of over 50 million Naira, but not more than 200 million Naira, including working capital but excluding cost of land. In terms of sectors, Al-Muitaba (2021) and Opariopo and Tamarauebi (2021) affirm that MSMEs play a vital role in the economic development of any country, both developed and developing.

Taxation is one of the most vital government instruments for revenue generation, redistribution of income, and regulation of business activity. Appah and Duoduo (2023b) suggested that taxes are mandatory contributions made by citizens of any society to the state subject to the jurisdiction of the government, for reasons of residence or property, and the revenue generated is for the provision of social goods and services for the economic growth and development of that society. According to Doyle (2022), taxes are used to fund public services, facilitate the redistribution of wealth and influence the behaviour of taxpayers. According to Gunel and Didinmez (2023), revenues from taxation make up the largest share of government revenue for developing countries. Through taxes, governments mobilise funds to provide critical public goods and services such as infrastructure, education, healthcare, and security. However, beyond its fiscal policy function, taxation also has a behavioural dimension that significantly

affects business decision-making, compliance, and performance. This behavioural aspect, referred to as behavioural taxation, deals with taxpayers' attitudes, perceptions, moral reasoning, social norms, and psychological responses toward tax obligations (Alabi et al, 2024; Vincent, 2021). When owners of MSMEs perceive the tax system as fair, simple, and transparent, they are more likely to comply voluntarily, leading to stable operations and improved performance (Agbi et al, 2024). On the contrary perceived injustice, corruption, or excessive tax burden can trigger tax evasion or avoidance, thereby undermining both compliance and firm sustainability (Ilodigwe, 2023).

In Nigeria, the issue of tax compliance among MSMEs remains a pressing concern. Many MSME owners view taxation as punitive rather than developmental, citing multiple taxation, inadequate taxpayer education, and poor tax administration as major disincentives to compliance (Oloyede et al, 2022). Studies have shown that behavioural determinants such as tax morale, attitude towards government, and perceived behavioural control significantly affect MSMEs compliance behaviour and performance outcomes (Alabi et al, 2024; Vincent, 2021). Nonetheless, empirical evidence directly connecting behavioural taxation to organizational performance measured through growth and operational performance remains limited, particularly within the Nigerian MSME sector. Given, that MSMEs are central to

Nigeria's socio-economic development, understanding how behavioural taxation impact organizational performance is necessary. Such understanding can inform tax policy reforms, improve taxpayer education, and foster a more enabling environment that improves MSME productivity, competitiveness, and survival. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the link between behavioural taxation and organizational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, providing insights into how behavioural determinants shape compliance and performance outcomes.

Statement of the problem

Micro, small and medium scale enterprises (MSMEs) play a key role in Nigeria's economic development, contributing over 50% to the national GDP and accounting about 90% of businesses and 80% of employment (SMEDAN, 2022). Notwithstanding this significant position, MSMEs in Nigeria face serious challenges that hinder their growth, competitiveness, and sustainability. One of the most recurrent challenges identified in empirical studies is taxation, principally the behavioural aspects of how entrepreneurs observe, recognize, and respond to tax policies and administration (Adeniran & Olayinka, 2023; Ezenwa & Nwosu, 2022). While much of the prior studies focused on conventional issues such as multiple taxation, tax policy complexity, and compliance burdens (Okafor et al, 2021; Akinyemi & Adewale, 2023), there is limited empirical commitment to behavioural taxation,

that is, how psychological, social, and cognitive reasons impact taxpayers' choices that eventually impact business outcomes. Behavioural taxation encompasses variables such as tax attitude, perceived fairness, tax morale, subjective norms, and behavioural intention to comply (Kircher, 2007). Studies across other societies show that these behavioural factors can shape compliance and investment decisions (Torgler & Schleiden, 2009), but there is insufficient understanding of how these determinants connects enterprise performance within the Nigerian MSMEs context. Recent empirical evidence disclose that behavioural factors have a significant influence on tax compliance among Nigerian entrepreneurs. For example, Olabisi et al (2023) revealed that taxpayers' attitudes, perceived behavioural control, and subjective norms significantly predict their intention to pay presumptive tax among informal SMEs in Nigeria. Likewise, Adedeji and Lawal (2024) found that tax morale that is driven by perceived fairness and trust in tax authorities significantly, influences compliance behaviour among SMEs in South – West Nigeria. However, these studies primarily measure behavioral taxation outcomes in terms of compliance rather than business performance. Consequently, the connection between behavioural tax factors and indicators such as profitability, business growth, and sustainability remains underexplored. Additionally, taxation in Nigeria is often perceived as unfair and burdensome,

particularly among MSMEs that operate under multiple tax jurisdictions. This perception shapes tax attitudes and compliance behaviour, which may in turn affect business reinvestment decisions, productivity, and performance (Eze & Umeji, 2022) The lack of a supportive tax culture and effective behavioural engagement mechanisms aggravate these challenges, leading to low tax morale, informalization of business operations, and stagnation in enterprise growth (Anaba & Oboh, 2021). Notwithstanding the relevance of these behavioural dimensions, there is a paucity of empirical studies that integrates behavioral taxation constructs into performance models of MSMEs in Nigeria. Most prior empirical evidence used traditional economic or compliance-based approaches to tax systems influence firm-level outcomes (Udo & Nnaji, 2023). Furthermore, the few studies that consider behavioural aspects are often cross-sectional, lack regional disaggregation, and do not capture heterogeneity among MSMEs. Therefore, the central problem this study seeks to address is the limited understanding of how behavioural taxation dimensions such as tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government affect the performance of MSMEs in Nigeria. Without such understanding, policymakers and tax authorities may continue to design and implement fiscal interventions that fail to motivate compliance, improve productivity, or stimulate sustainable business performance in the MSMEs sector.

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to investigate behavioural taxation on the organisational performance of micro, small, and medium enterprises in Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To investigate the relationship between tax morale and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.
2. To evaluate the relationship between procedural fairness and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.
3. To ascertain the relationship between distributive fairness and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.
4. To determine the relationship between trust in government and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions were analysed in this study:

1. What is the relationship between tax morale and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between procedural fairness and the growth and

operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?

3. What is the relationship between distributive fairness and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?

4. What is the relationship between trust in government and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in this study:

Ho₁: There is no statistically significant relationship between tax morale and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no statistically significant relationship between procedural fairness and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Ho₃: There is no statistically significant relationship between distributive fairness and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Ho₄: There is no statistically significant relationship between trust in government and the growth and operational performance of MSMEs in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Justification of the Study

This study is justified because MSMEs are the backbone of Nigeria's non-oil economy but face challenges of low productivity, informality and inconsistent tax compliance (SMEDAN, 2022).

Existing tax research in Nigeria focuses on structural determinants such as tax rates, enforcement, and multiple taxation, while behavioural taxation that examines attitudes, norms, trust, fairness, and moral obligations remains underexplored (Agbetunde et al, 2020). Tax behaviour directly and indirectly affects MSME performance by influencing compliance costs, profitability, business confidence, and willingness to expand (Oloyede, et al, 2025). Understanding behavioural taxation helps tax authorities design policies that improve compliance and MSME performance through trust-based, fair and simplified tax systems. A review of extant literature reveals that most Nigerian tax studies apply deterrence theory or the fiscal exchange theory focusing on sanctions and enforcement. Few studies apply behavioural economics theories to explain why MSMEs comply or do not. While several studies have explored tax compliance determinants (Ataswodi & Ojeka, 2012; Ellawule et al, 2024), very few have empirically investigated the connection between behavioural taxation and MSME performance, particularly in relation to growth and sustainability indicators. Also, behavioural taxation studies in developed nations (e.g., Torgler, 2007; Kirchler et al, 2008) cannot be directly applied to Nigeria due to differences in governance trust, institutional quality, and tax morale. Thus, a localized empirical investigation is necessary to reflect

Nigeria's socio-economic and institutional realities. Therefore, this study addresses these gaps by integrating behavioural and performance dimensions of MSMEs using Nigeria data. This study holds substantial policy relevance for tax authorities (such as Nigerian Revenue Service), understanding behavioural drivers among MSMEs enables designing more effective compliance strategies (education, trust-building, fairness perceptions). For MSME support agencies and government business interface, insight into how tax behaviour affects business viability can lead to supportive interventions. Given Nigeria's need to diversify revenue sources and formalize more MSMEs, improving compliance behaviour among MSMEs contributes both to revenue generation and enterprise growth. Thus, by connecting behavioural taxation with MSME performance, policy makers can craft integrative interventions that serve dual goals; tax base expansion and MSME development. Also, this study contributes to the advancement of behavioural taxation literature into the MSME context in a developing nation. The study also provides empirical evidence on how behavioural tax factors influence firm performance outcomes (which is less explored). Therefore, this study has both theoretical and empirical significance for scholarships.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework Authors Creation

Concept of Behavioural Taxation:

Behavioural taxation is the study and application of behavioural economics and psychology principles to understand how taxpayers’ attitudes, perceptions, beliefs, social norms, trust, and cognitive biases influence their tax-related decisions, such as compliance, evasion, or avoidance. It explains why and how taxpayers behave the way they do, that is, beyond the traditional economic assumption that people are purely rational actors responding only to tax rates, penalties, and audit risks. Weber et al (2014) define behavioural taxation as an approach to understanding taxpayers’ behaviour by combining behavioural economics and psychology into taxation research and policy. Alm and Kasper (2023) explain that behavioural taxation shows the role of non-economic motives such as fairness, trust,

tax morale, and social norms in shaping compliance behaviour. AbdelNabi et al (2024) describe it as the study of taxpayer behaviour that combines behavioural understandings into tax administration to enhance voluntary compliance. Hauptman et al (2024) add that behavioural taxation connects taxpayers’ motivational postures and behavioural goals to comply with outcomes, emphasizing psychological and governance factors rather than pure enforcement. Alabi et al (2024) view behavioural taxation as the psychological and moral dimensions of taxation, which determine an SME owner’s willingness to comply with tax obligations, influenced by tax morale, fairness perception, and trust in authorities. Consequently, behavioural taxation is based on the idea that tax compliance is not determined by deterrence alone, but a mixture of several

behavioural and psychological factors such as tax morale, fairness perception, trust in tax authorities, social norms, tax knowledge and awareness, perceived behavioural control, and behavioural biases. Ojo and Shittu (2023) observed that behavioural perceptions are important for designing SME tax policies that foster voluntary compliance and improve tax revenue generation. This study used tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government as constructs for behavioural taxation. **Tax morale** refers to the intrinsic motivation or moral obligation individuals feel to pay taxes, beyond the fear of penalties or the probability of being audited. It represents the psychological, ethical, and cultural willingness of taxpayers to comply with tax laws voluntarily. According to Alabi et al (2024), tax morale reflects the psychological and moral disposition of SME owners toward tax payment, shaped by fairness, trust, and government accountability. Also, Cummings et al (2022) state that tax morale reflects taxpayers' intrinsic motivation, and trust in influencing their willingness to comply voluntarily. Empirical studies show that tax morale is influenced by several psychological, cultural, and institutional factors. Alabi et al (2024) revealed that tax morale significantly affects compliance among SMEs in Lagos, influenced by fairness and trust. Also, Ojo and Shittu (2023) disclosed that attitude and perception of justice shape tax compliance under Nigerian VAT regime. Similarly, David

and Bello (2025) showed that awareness and moral responsibility predict compliance among informal-sector taxpayers in Oyo State. **Procedural fairness**, also called procedural justice, refers to the perceived fairness of the processes, procedures, and methods used by authorities when making decisions that affect individuals. In the context of taxation, procedural fairness relates to how taxpayers perceive assessment, collection, dispute resolution, and enforcement, that is, whether they are transparent, consistent, unbiased, and respectful. According to Feld and Frey (2007), in taxation, procedural fairness is the perception that tax authorities treat taxpayers with respect, follow clear rules, and make decisions transparently. Similarly, Kirchler et al (2008) described procedural fairness in tax administration as involving trustworthy, consistent, and neutral procedures, which enhance voluntary compliance. **Distributive fairness**, also called distributive justice, refers to the perceived fairness of how resources, rewards, or outcomes are distributed among individuals or groups within a system, organization, or society. It is concerned with who gets what and whether that distribution is fair according to certain principles such as equality, equity, or need. Distributive fairness as framed under the broader umbrella of behavioural taxation relates to how taxpayers perceive the fairness of how tax burdens and tax benefits are allocated. People's perceptions of fairness influence their attitudes and behaviours

toward tax compliance. Wenzel (2003) found that perceived fairness in tax outcomes positively affects voluntary compliance, even beyond the effects of procedural fairness. **Trust in government** refers to citizens' confidence in the integrity, competence, and benevolence of public institutions and officials to act in the best interests of society. It reflects a belief that government authorities are fair, honest, and capable of making decisions that serve the public good (OECD, 2017). In other words, trust in government is a psychological and social attitude through which citizens accept government actions as legitimate and are willing to cooperate voluntarily with state institutions. Trust in government plays a vital role in shaping taxpayers' attitudes and behaviour toward compliance. When citizens believe that government institutions are fair, transparent, and use tax revenues responsibly, they are more willing to pay taxes voluntarily (Kirchler, 2007). Trust forms part of what Feld and Frey (2007) call the psychological tax contract, in which taxpayers perceive a reciprocal connection between themselves and the state. Ajibola and Lateef (2023) identify trust in government as one key drivers of tax compliance behaviour in Nigeria. Oloruntoba (2021) found that trust in government significantly influence voluntary tax compliance in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Concept of Organisational Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises:

Organizational performance refers to an organisation's ability to achieve its objectives by

effectively and efficiently using its resources, generating outputs and outcomes that align with stakeholder expectations. According to Orishdede (2024), organizational performance is the overall effectiveness of an organization in terms of doing its daily responsibilities and achieving its predetermined goals. Adebayo et al (2024) describes organizational performance as the efficiency and effectiveness with which an organization meets its goals. The authors further noted that performance metrics often include financial results, market share, customer satisfaction, and innovation rates. Similarly, Kimotho and Kariuki (2024) state that organizational performance refers to the assessment of how effectively an organization achieves goals and objectives are attained using a comprehensive measure of how well an organization uses its resources to produce desired outcomes, deliver value to stakeholders, and sustain its competitiveness in the market. In the words of Elbadawy et al (2024), organizational performance is the degree to which a firm accomplishes its objectives outlined in the strategic plan, encompassing all aspects of operations, including financial, operational, and competitive success. Current study emphasizes that performance is multidimensional, going beyond financial results to include process efficiency, customer satisfaction, innovation capability, and sustainability (Contu, 2020; Kimotho & Kariuki, 2024). It involves the transformation of inputs into outputs within a given timeframe while

meeting internal and external requirements of effectiveness and efficiency. In the era of fast change in the environment and digitalization, organizational performance is increasingly regarded as dynamic, that is, shaped by strategic management, resilience, and adaptive capabilities rather than static outcome measures (Biswakarma & Bohora, 2025; Rexhepi & Berisha, 2025). This study used growth performance and operational performance as measures of organizational performance.

Growth performance refers to an organisation's ability to expand its scale or scope while simultaneously achieving effective performance results such as profitability, efficiency, and market value. It is the capacity of a firm to expand via growth in sales, assets, employment, market share while achieving or improving performance outcomes (Osime et al, 2020; Ijeoma, 2021; Ofurum & Obi, 2023).

Operational performance refers to the efficiency and effectiveness with which an organization executes its core business operations (Agbi et al, 2024). It measures how well resources such as labour, materials, technology, and processes are employed to produce goods or services, achieve quality, meet deadlines, and satisfy customer expectations (Ofoegbu & Efeh, 2023). Operational performance often focuses on metrics like productivity, efficiency, quality, cycle time, and cost control (Olumoh, 2024; Ofoegbu & Efeh, 2023).

Theoretical Review

This study is grounded on the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) advanced by Ajzen (1991). The theory posits that an individual's behaviour is directly influenced by their behavioural intention, which is, in turn, affected by an individual's positive or negative evaluation of performing a behaviour (Ajzen, 2015). According to Abubakar and Baba (2024), in taxation, a taxpayer's attitude reflects whether they perceive paying taxes as beneficial or harmful. Alabi et al (2024) argue that a positive attitude toward tax compliance increases the likelihood of tax-paying behaviour. Ban-Kalid et al (2022) maintain that subjective norms involve perceived social pressure to perform or not perform a behaviour. Kristy et al (2022) stress that in the context of taxation, this includes the influence of peers, family, or society on whether a person complies with tax laws. If significant others approve of tax compliance, individuals are more likely to adhere to tax regulations (Kirchler, 2007). Shaharuddin et al (2023) note that perceived behavioural control refers to the perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour, like self-efficacy. Taxpayers' perception of their ability to comply with tax laws affects their intention and actual compliance (Oseifuah, 2025). Lawal et al (2025) argue that higher perceived behavioural control is generally associated with higher compliance. According to Alabi et al (2024), a positive taxation environment and high compliance can improve MSME productivity, profitability and growth. In the context of behavioural taxation,

TPB has been effectively applied to understand why taxpayers, including MSMEs, comply or fail to comply with tax obligations. The attitude towards tax compliance reflects how favourably or unfavourably business owners evaluate paying taxes. In Nigeria, MSMEs attitudes are often shaped by perceptions of fairness, government accountability, and the benefits derived from tax revenue. Studies show that positive attitudes promote compliance, though in some Nigerian cases, attitudes were found to be less influenced than social and control factors (Gimba & Ibrahim, 2017). In the Nigerian MSMEs environment, peer influence, professional associations, and community expectations play a vital role. The study of Abubakar and Baba (2024) revealed that subjective norms are a consistent and significant predictor of MSMEs' intention to pay taxes.

Empirical Review

Etang et al (2025) investigated multiple taxation on the financial performance and compliance behaviour of SMEs in Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive and causal research design with a population consisting of registered SMEs operating in Lagos, Abuja, Port Harcourt, Kano and Enugu. The study employed a multi-stage sampling method, stratified random sampling and a sample size of 400 SMEs using Yamene's formula. The study used primary data collected through the administration of structured questionnaires, and the questionnaire was validated using a pilot study. The data collected from the questionnaire were

analysed using descriptive statistics, multiple regression, and binary logistic regression. Financial performance as the dependent variable, multiple taxation as the independent variable, and firm size, age and sector as control variables. The findings reveal a statistically significant negative relationship between multiple taxation and SME financial performance, as well as a strong inverse link between tax multiplicity and tax compliance. The study confirms that uncoordinated and excessive tax burdens reduce profitability, discourage business reinvestment, and increase the likelihood of non-compliance.

Oloyede et al (2024) explored taxation and performance of SMEs in Nigeria. The study employed a survey research design with a population of 42,067, and the Taro Yamane method was used to determine the sample size of 396 participants. Primary and secondary sources of data collection were used, and questionnaires were the major instrument of data collection. The study employed taxation measured by tax policy, tax administration, multiple taxation and tax incentives as independent variables while performance was measured by effectiveness, productivity, efficiency and profitability. The data collected from the self-administered questionnaire responses were analysed using descriptive analysis, correlation analysis and ANOVA. The findings showed a significantly positive link between tax policy and the effectiveness of SMEs in Nigeria, but tax administration had no

significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in Nigeria. The study results further disclosed that multiple taxation showed a significantly positive link to the productivity of SMEs in Nigeria, and tax incentives significantly impact the efficiency of SMEs in Nigeria. The study concluded that tax policy, tax incentives and multiple taxation influence the performance of SMEs in Nigeria. Still, tax administration did not affect the performance of SMEs in Nigeria.

Nwanne et al (2023) explored infrastructure and taxation on the performance of micro and small enterprises in Nigeria. The study employed a survey research design with a population of 370 randomly selected MSEs using a simple random sampling technique to determine the sample size of 185. The study adopts primary and secondary sources of data collection. The primary data were obtained from a well-structured questionnaire using a four-point Likert scale administered to respondents. The data obtained were analysed using descriptive statistics and chi-square statistics. The inferential statistical analysis revealed that electricity supply had a positive and significant effect on the profitability of MSEs, road infrastructure had a significant positive effect on product and service delivery of MSEs, and taxation had no significant positive effects on the performance of micro and small enterprises in Calabar Metropolis.

Appah and Duoduo (2023a) evaluated the determinants of tax compliance behaviour on sustainable economic growth of micro, small

and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in South-South, Nigeria. The study employed a cross-sectional survey research design with a sample of MSMEs in South-South, Nigeria. The primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale and a sample size of 535 using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. The data collected from the administered questionnaires were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis. The findings from the regression analysis showed a significantly positive link between tax penalty and sustainable economic growth among MSMEs in south-south of Nigeria; a significantly positive link between tax fairness and sustainable economic growth among MSMEs in south-south of Nigeria; a significantly negative link between perceived opportunities of tax evasion and sustainable economic growth among MSMEs in south-south of Nigeria; a significantly positive link between tax audit and sustainable economic growth among MSMEs in south-south of Nigeria; and a significantly positive link between tax system and sustainable economic growth among MSMEs in south-south of Nigeria. Therefore, the study concluded that tax determinants influence the compliance behaviour of MSMEs in Nigeria.

Enang et al (2022) examined taxation and performance of SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study employed a survey research design with a population of 11,663 SMEs in Epe, Ikeja,

Badagry, Lagos Island, and Ikorodu, Lagos State, and the Taro Yamane standard formula was adopted for the determination of a sample size of 387 SMEs. Data was collected from primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected from a structured questionnaire using a Likert scale from strongly agree to strongly disagree administered to participants with personal interviews, while the secondary data was collected from records and other publications. The study used tax rate and tax compliance as independent variables and performance as a dependent variable. The responses obtained from the administered questionnaires were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The multiple regression analysis revealed an inverse association between tax rate and tax compliance on the performance of SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. Also, tax incentives showed a significantly positive link to the performance of SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Udeh et al (2022) carried out a study of multiple taxation and the growth of SMEs in Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design. The population of this study covered 7,844 MSMEs registered with the SMEDAN in South-South States, Nigeria and a sample size of 381 SMEs was drawn using Taro Yamane's standard formula using the Bowley formula. The sample size was stratified to Akwa-Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers State in South-South Nigeria. The study employed primary and secondary sources of data, and the primary data

were obtained from a structured questionnaire after validity testing using Cronbach's Alpha. The study used consumption taxes, environmental and sanitation levies, infrastructure development levy and property and land-based charges as independent variables while growth was the dependent variable. The data obtained from the questionnaire administered were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis. The findings of the multiple regression analysis reveal that consumption taxes, environmental and sanitation levies, infrastructure development levy and property levies significantly affect growth in SMEs in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design with an explanatory (causal) orientation. The descriptive aspect helps to assess and describe the existing behavioural taxation practices among MSMEs, while the explanatory component investigates the effect of these behaviours on enterprise performance. The survey design is appropriate because it allows the researcher to collect data from many respondents at a single point in time and to analyse patterns of relationships among variables using statistical methods. This study employed a quantitative approach. This approach is preferred because it enables the testing of hypotheses and generalization of findings to the broader MSMEs population in Nigeria. The target population of this research

comprises all MSMEs operating in Nigeria, as defined by the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) and the National Bureau of Statistics. The population comprised of 386,655 registered SMEs in Nigeria. The sample size of 399 participants was determined using Taro Yamene's (1967) formula for a known population. A stratified random sampling technique was adopted to ensure adequate representation of different categories of MSMEs. Each stratum was proportionately represented. Within each stratum, enterprises were randomly selected using a simple random method. For the qualitative aspect, purposive sampling was used to select business owners, tax consultants, and officials of Nigerian Revenue Service for in-depth interviews. Primary data was collected using structured questionnaires administered to MSME owners/managers. The questionnaire contains closed-ended Likert-scale items designed to measure behavioural taxation constructs and performance indicators. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected respondents to gather qualitative insights into taxation behaviour and performance challenges. Secondary data was obtained from existing literature, including reports and publications from SMEDAN, NBS, and NBS. Journal and academic articles on taxation and MSMEs performance. Also, relevant government policy documents and statistical reports were used. The major instrument for data collection was a structured

questionnaire, divided into three sections of demographic information, behavioural taxation and MSMEs performance using a five-point Likert scale of strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2) and strongly disagree (1). The study used face and content validity to ensure that items adequately covered the study objectives. Also, construct validity was used to ensure that the questionnaire items aligned with existing validated scales from prior studies on tax behaviour and SME performance. A pilot study was conducted on 30 MSMEs to test the reliability of the instrument, and the data collected was analysed using Cronbach's Alpha for internal consistency and a coefficient value of 0.70 or higher was considered acceptable for reliability. However, when questionnaires were distributed to participants for data collection, 325 participants responded to the questionnaires distributed for this study. A total of 314 questionnaires were used for data analysis. As a result, 74 respondents failed to return the questionnaires, and 11 questionnaires were not properly filled out by the respondents. This means the response rate for questionnaires was 79%. The data was analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and Eview, and descriptive statistic (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations to summarize data), correlation analysis (to examine simple relationship between behavioural taxation components and performance), and regression analysis (to test the effect of behavioural taxation components

and performance) were performed to test hypotheses. The hypotheses were tested using the regression coefficient and p-values.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics of Measuring Instrument

Construct	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha
Tax Morale (TAM)	5	0.82
Procedural Fairness (PDF)	5	0.72
Distributive Fairness (DTF)	5	0.86
Trust in Government (TIG)	5	0.84
Growth performance (GRP)	5	0.72
Operational Performance (OPP)	5	0.88

Source: Authors Creation (2025)

The multiple regression was guided by a linear model below:

$$GRP = \beta_0 + \beta_1TAM + \beta_2PDF + \beta_3DTF + \beta_4TIG + e \text{-----}$$

---- (1)

$$OPP = \beta_0 + \beta_1TAM + \beta_2PDF + \beta_3DTF + \beta_4TIG + e \text{-----}$$

---- (2)

Results and Discussion of Findings

Data Presentation

Table 2: Questionnaire Distribution

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Number Retrieved	314	78.7	78.7	78.7
Number not retrieved	74	18.5	18.5	97.2
Number not properly filed	11	2.8	2.8	100.0
Total	399	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 shows the distribution and collection of questionnaires sent to the respondents. It was

The primary data was collected from respondents using the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed and later retrieved by the respondents. The primary data collected was then subjected to analysis. In testing the hypotheses of the study, the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) multiple regression was used. From the sample, 399 copies of the questionnaire were distributed.

shown that 399 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, representing 100%. 314

questionnaires representing 78.7% were correctly filled and successfully retrieved from the respondents; however, 74 questionnaires

representing 18.5% were not retrieved, and 11 questionnaires representing 2.8% were not properly filed.

Table 3: Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	184	58.5	58.5	58.5
Female	130	41.5	41.5	100.0
Total	314	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 shows the gender of respondents in the sample of the study. 58.5% which translates to 281 respondents, are male, while 41.5%, which translates to 130 respondents, are female. This

implies that there is a diverse gender representation among the target respondents in MSMEs in Nigeria.

Table 4: Age Range

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18 – 25 years	52	16.6	16.6	16.6
26 – 35 years	113	36.0	36.0	52.6
36 – 45 years	65	20.7	20.7	73.3
46 – 55 years	58	18.5	18.5	91.8
56 and above years	26	8.2	8.2	100.0
Total	314	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 shows the age range of respondents. It was shown that 52 respondents representing 16.6% are between the age brackets of 18 – 25 years, 113 respondents representing 36.0% are between the age bracket of 26 – 35 years, 65 respondents representing 20.7% are between

the age bracket of 36 – 45 years, 58 respondents representing 18.5% are between the age bracket of 46 – 55 years, 26 respondents representing 8.2% are between the age bracket of 56 and above years.

Table 5: Educational Qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid OND/HND	69	22.0	22.3	22.0
Bachelor’s Degree	112	35.7	35.7	57.7
Master’s Degree	71	22.6	22.6	80.3
Doctorate Degree	24	7.6	7.6	87.9
Professional Certification	38	12.1	12.1	100.0
Total	314	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 presents the educational qualifications of respondents. It shows that 69 respondents representing 22.0% possess ordinary national diploma and higher national diploma, 112 respondents representing 35.7% possess bachelor’s degree, 71 respondents representing 22.6% possess master’s degree, 24 respondents representing 7.6% possess doctorate degree and

38 respondents representing 12.1% possess professional certificate. The cumulative percentage indicates the progressive accumulation of respondents across different educational levels, reaching 100% for all categories combined. This distribution offers insights into the educational backgrounds of the study sample.

Table 6: Years of Business Operations

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Less than One Year	61	19.4	19.4	19.4
1 – 3 years	118	37.6	37.6	57.0
4 – 6 years	59	18.8	18.8	75.8
7 – 10 years	43	13.7	13.7	89.5
Over 10 years	33	10.5	10.5	100.0
Total	314	100.0	100.0	

Table 6 shows the Years of Business Operations of respondents. It was shown that 61 respondents representing 19.4% have less than one of year business operations, 118 respondents representing 37.6% have between 1

– 3 years of business operations, 59 respondents representing 18.8% have between 4 – 6 years of business operations, 43 respondents representing 13.7% have between 7 – 10 years of business operations, and 33 respondents

representing 10.5% have over 10 years of business operations.

Table 7: Business Sector/Industry

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agriculture	45	14.3	14.3	14.3
Manufacturing	83	24.4	24.4	38.7
Wholesale/Retail	102	34.5	34.5	73.2
Service	61	19.4	19.4	92.6
Construction	23	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	314	100.0	100.0	

Table 7 shows the Business Sector/Industry of respondents. It was shown that 45 respondents representing 14.3% are involved in Agriculture, 83 respondents representing 24.4% are involved in manufacturing, 102 respondents representing

34.5% are involved wholesale/retail, 61 respondents representing 19.4% are involved in service, and 23 respondents representing 7.4% are involved in construction.

Table 8: Type of Taxes Applicable

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Personal Income Tax	105	33.4	33.4	33.4
Company Income Tax	68	21.7	21.7	55.1
Value Added Tax	65	20.7	20.7	75.8
Local Government Levies	60	19.1	19.1	94.9
Others	16	5.1	5.1	100.0
Total	314	100.0	100.0	

Table 8 shows the types of tax applicable of respondents. It was shown that 105 respondents representing 33.4% pay personal income tax, 68 respondents representing 21.7% pay company income tax, 65 respondents representing 20.7%

pay value added tax, 60 respondents representing 19.1% pay local government levies, and 16 respondents representing 5.1% pay other types of taxes.

Table 9: Type of Business Ownership

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Sole proprietor	123	39.2	39.2	39.2
Partnership	93	29.6	29.6	68.8
Limited Liability Company	25	8.0	8.0	76.8
Cooperative	40	12.7	12.7	89.5
Others	33	10.5	10.5	100.0
Total	314	100.0	100.0	

Table 9 shows the type of business ownership of respondents. It was shown that 123 respondents representing 39.2% are involved in sole proprietorship business, 93 respondents representing 29.6% are involved in partnership business, 25 respondents representing 8.0% are

involved in limited liability company business, 40 respondents representing 12.7% are involved in cooperative business, and 33 respondents representing 10.5% are involved in other types of business ownership that integrates all the above.

Table 10: Descriptive Statistics of Tax Morale

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	I believe paying taxes is a civic duty that every responsible citizen should fulfil	314	1.00	5.00	3.709	1.315
2	Paying taxes is essential for the government to provide good public service	314	1.00	5.00	3.486	1.303
3	The government has the right to demand taxes from all income-earning citizens	314	1.00	5.00	3.522	1.300
4	I am more likely to pay taxes if I trust that the government uses tax money wisely.	314	1.00	5.00	3.717	1.227
5	I would pay my taxes even if there were little chance of being caught for non-payment.	314	1.00	5.00	3.932	1.210
Valid N (listwise)		314			3.673	1.271

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The results in table 10 depicted the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on tax morale variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items were labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to

determine the overall mean and standard deviation of responses on tax morale. Notwithstanding all the items, the mean cut-off points of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.673; Std. D =1.271**) respectively.

Table 11: Descriptive Statistics of Procedural Fairness

S/ N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	The procedures for assessment and payment are transparent and easy to understand	314	1.00	5.00	3.546	1.143
2	Tax officials are polite, respectful, and professional when dealing with taxpayers	314	1.00	5.00	3.865	1.342
3	The tax authority provides clear explanations for tax assessed	314	1.00	5.00	3.224	1.325
4	Tax officials apply rules and penalties fairly without discrimination	314	1.00	5.00	3.543	1.352
5	I am satisfied with the fairness of the overall tax administration process in Nigeria	314	1.00	5.00	3.751	1.421
Valid N (listwise)		314			3.586	1.317

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The results in table 11 showed the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on procedural fairness variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items were labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to

determine the overall mean and standard deviation of responses on procedural fairness. Notwithstanding all the items, the mean cut-off points of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.586; Std. D =1.317**) respectively.

Table 12: Descriptive Statistics of Distributive Fairness

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	The taxes I pay are fair considering the profits or income my business earns.	314	1.00	5.00	3.609	1.308
2	The current tax system in Nigeria distributes the tax burden fairly among all taxpayers	314	1.00	5.00	3.741	1.318
3	I believe that those who earn more should pay a higher proportion of taxes	314	1.00	5.00	3.773	1.379
4	I am satisfied with the fairness of how tax burdens and benefits are shared in Nigeria.	314	1.00	5.00	3.661	1.200
5	The distribution of tax incentives is fair to all business categories	314	1.00	5.00	3.470	1.278
Valid N (listwise)		314			3.651	1.297

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The results in table 12 presented the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on distributive fairness variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items were labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to

determine the overall mean and standard deviation of responses on distributive fairness. Notwithstanding all the items, the mean cut-off points of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.651; Std. D =1.297**) respectively.

Table 13: Descriptive Statistics of Trust in Government

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	I believe that tax revenues are used to provide essential public services such as infrastructure, education, and healthcare.	314	1.00	5.00	3.521	1.400
2	I am confident that taxes collected are used to improve the business environment in Nigeria.	314	1.00	5.00	3.992	1.226
3	I feel confident that my tax payments contribute to national development	314	1.00	5.00	3.884	1.109
4	I believe the Nigerian government uses tax revenues for the benefit of citizens	314	1.00	5.00	3.880	1.256

5	I have confidence in the Nigerian government’s management of tax resources	314	1.00	5.00	3.761	1.248
Valid N (listwise)		314			3.808	1.248

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The results in table 13 disclosed the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on trust in government variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items were labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to

determine the overall mean and standard deviation of responses on trust in government. Notwithstanding all the items, the mean cut-off points of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.808; Std. D =1.248**) respectively.

Table 14: Descriptive Statistics of Growth Performance

S/ N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	My business has experienced steady growth in sales revenue over the past three years	314	1.00	5.00	3.423	1.312
2	The profit level of my business has increased consistently in recent years	314	1.00	5.00	3.763	1.324
3	The number of customers or clients patronizing my business has grown over time.	314	1.00	5.00	3.125	1.432
4	My business has expanded its market share within the local market	314	1.00	5.00	3.523	1.325
5	The productivity of my employees has improved significantly in the past few years	314	1.00	5.00	3.568	1.421
Valid N (listwise)		314			3.480	1.363

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The results in table 14 revealed the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on growth performance variable

using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items were labelled, and the mean

and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation of responses on growth performance. Notwithstanding all the items, the

mean cut-off points of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.480; Std. D =1.363**) respectively.

Table 15: Descriptive Statistics of Operational Performance

S/ N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	The reliability and consistency of our service or product delivery have improved.	314	1.00	5.00	3.609	1.293
2	Innovation in processes, products, or services has enhanced operational efficiency	314	1.00	5.00	3.812	1.268
3	My business has reduced operational and production costs in recent years	314	1.00	5.00	3.609	1.365
4	The quality of our products or services has significantly improved.	314	1.00	5.00	3.581	1.273
5	My business consistently meets delivery schedules and customer deadlines.	314	1.00	5.00	3.601	1.290
Valid N (listwise)		314			3.642	1.298

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The results in table 15 showed the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on operational performance variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items were labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were

calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation of responses on operational performance. Notwithstanding all the items, the mean cut-off points of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.642; Std. D =1.298**) respectively.

Table 16: Correlation Matrix

	GRP	TAM	PDF	DTF	TIG
GRP Pearson Correlation	1				
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00				
N	314				

TAM	Pearson Correlation	0.724	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000			
	N	314	314			
PDF	Pearson Correlation	0.636	0.546	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		
	N	314	314	314		
DTF	Pearson Correlation	0.626	0.646	0.574	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	314	314	314	314	
TIG	Pearson Correlation	0.643	0.624	0.568	0.584	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	314	314	314	314	314

Source: Computed by Author via SPSS (2025)

The bivariate analysis was carried out using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC), showing the relationship between behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) and organizational performance (growth performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. Table 16 displays a strong and positive ($r = 0.724$, $P = 0.00$) association between tax morale and growth performance of

MSMEs in Nigeria, a strong and positive ($r = 0.636$, $P = 0.00$) relationship between link between procedural fairness and growth performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, a strong and positive ($r = 0.626$, $P = 0.00$) relationship between distributive fairness and growth of MSMEs in Nigeria and a strong and positive ($r = 0.643$, $P = 0.00$) relationship between trust in government and growth of MSMEs in Nigeria.

Table 17: Correlation Matrix

		OPP	TAM	PDF	DTF	TIG
OPP	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00				
	N	314				
TAM	Pearson Correlation	0.642	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000			
	N	314	314			
PDF	Pearson Correlation	0.684	0.642	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		
	N	314	314	314		

DTF	Pearson Correlation	0.624	0.652	0.548	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	314	314	314	314	
TIG	Pearson Correlation	0.714	0.664	0.582	0.628	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	314	314	314	314	314

Source: Computed by Author via SPSS (2025)

The Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) showed the relationship between behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) and organizational performance (operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. Table 17 displays a strong and positive ($r = 0.642, P = 0.00$) association between tax morale and operational performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, a strong and

positive ($r = 0.684, P = 0.00$) relationship between link between procedural fairness and operational performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, a strong and positive ($r = 0.624, P = 0.00$) relationship between distributive fairness and operational performance of MSMEs in Nigeria and a strong and positive ($r = 0.714, P = 0.00$) link between trust in government and operational performance of MSMEs in Nigeria.

Table 18: Multiple Regression Analysis Model One

Dependent Variable: GRP

Method: Least Squares

Date: 12/13/25 Time: 16:22

Sample(adjusted): 1 314

Included observations: 314 after adjusting endpoints

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.275444	2.256856	1.451330	0.1488
TAM	1.287452	0.587612	2.190989	0.0182
PDF	1.382834	0.642347	2.152783	0.0227
DTF	1.238474	0.583415	2.122801	0.0374
TIG	1.234756	0.536937	2.299629	0.0364
R-squared	0.678752	Mean dependent var		12.99346
Adjusted R-squared	0.558347	S.D. dependent var		3.098167
S.E. of regression	2.888766	Akaike info criterion		4.997962

Sum squared resid	1226.711	Schwarz criterion	5.116803
Log likelihood	-376.3441	F-statistic	5.567008
Durbin-Watson stat	2.567232	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000100

Source: e-view output

Table 18 presents the multiple regression analysis for behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) and organizational performance (growth performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. The analysis suggests a positive and significant ($0.0182 < 0.05$) link between tax morale and growth performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, a positive and significant ($0.0227 < 0.05$) connection between procedural fairness and growth performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, a positive and significant ($0.0374 < 0.05$) association between distributive fairness and growth performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, and a positive and significant ($0.0364 < 0.05$) relationship between trust in government and growth performance of MSMEs in Nigeria. The R^2 (coefficient of determination) of 0.678752 and adjusted R^2 of 0.558347 shows that the variables combined determines about 68% and

56% of the relationship between behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) and organizational performance (operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. The F-statistics and its probability shows that the regression equation is well formulated explaining that the relationship between behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) variables combined affects organizational performance (growth performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria are statistically significant (F-stat = 5.567008; F-pro. = 0.000100). Therefore, the findings conclude that behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) had a significantly positive influence on organizational performance (growth performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria.

Table 19: Multiple Regression Analysis Model Two

Dependent Variable: OPP

Method: Least Squares

Date: 12/13/25 Time: 18:14

Sample(adjusted): 1 314

Included observations: 314 after adjusting endpoints

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.275444	2.256856	1.451330	0.1488
TAM	1.347352	0.628438	2.143969	0.0252

PDF	1.324284	0.589428	2.246727	0.0342
DTF	1.257212	0.582153	2.159590	0.0386
TIG	1.257328	0.578432	2.173683	0.0362
R-squared	0.542358	Mean dependent var		12.99346
Adjusted R-squared	0.425238	S.D. dependent var		3.098167
S.E. of regression	2.888766	Akaike info criterion		4.997962
Sum squared resid	1226.711	Schwarz criterion		5.116803
Log likelihood	-376.3441	F-statistic		5.567008
Durbin-Watson stat	2.238322	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000100

Source: e-view output

Table 19 presents the multiple regression analysis for behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) and organizational performance (operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. The analysis suggests a positive and significant ($0.0252 < 0.05$) link between tax morale and growth performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, a positive and significant ($0.0342 < 0.05$) connection between procedural fairness and operational performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, a positive and significant ($0.0386 < 0.05$) association between distributive fairness and operational performance of MSMEs in Nigeria, and a positive and significant ($0.0386 < 0.05$) relationship between trust in government and operational performance of MSMEs in Nigeria. The R^2 (coefficient of determination) of 0.542358 and adjusted R^2 of 0.425238 shows that the variables combined determines about 68% and 56% of the relationship between behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in

government) and organizational performance (operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. The F-statistics and its probability shows that the regression equation is well formulated explaining that the relationship between behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) variables combined affects organizational performance (operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria are statistically significant (F-stat = 5.567008; F-pro. = 0.000100). Therefore, the findings conclude that behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) had a significantly positive influence on organizational performance (operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Tax Morale and Organisational Performance: The study revealed a positive and significant relationship between tax morale and organizational performance (growth and operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria.

The result is consistent with prior studies of Alabi et al (2024), Ikidi et al (2024), and Lucky et al (2025). The studies showed that higher tax morale implies more compliance, and compliance is often a precondition for paying taxes correctly, which could reduce tax-related burdens and thereby indirectly assist in performance and growth. However, the study disagrees with Abdullahi et al (2025), Inim et al (2020). Abdullahi et al (2025) submit that multiple taxation has a significantly negative impact on SMEs growth. The result suggests that MSME operators who believe in the moral obligations to pay taxes tend to demonstrate better compliance attitudes. Higher tax morale reduces the likelihood of tax evasion and encourages timely fulfilment of tax obligations, resulting in fewer penalties, improved financial planning, and smoother business operations. This supports the idea that internalized civic values contribute meaningfully to organizational efficiency and long-term performance.

Procedural Fairness and Organisational Performance: The study revealed a positive and significant relationship between procedural fairness and organizational performance (growth and operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. The finding is consistent with the study carried out by Oyedele et al (2022), Oyeniyi and Okoughenu (2023). Nevertheless, the study negates the findings of Alawode and Adegbe (2022) that procedural justice has a negative but significant effect on

voluntary compliance outcome. When taxpayers believe that tax authorities treat them respectfully and provide clear guidelines, they are more willing to comply voluntarily. Such fairness reduces conflicts between businesses and regulators, minimizes compliance costs, and creates a predictable operating environment, which ultimately supports improved productivity and business stability.

Distributive Fairness and Organisational Performance: The study revealed a positive and significant relationship between distributive fairness and organizational performance (growth and operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. The study concurs with the findings of Oyedele et al (2025), Oyeniyi and Okoughenu (2023), Alawode and Adegbe (2022). Oyedele et al (2025) study revealed that tax justice significantly affects tax fairness perceptions among SMEs and significantly influences compliance. The result suggests that MSMEs are more likely to perceive tax payments as justifiable when they believe public funds are utilized efficiently and that they receive tangible benefits such as infrastructure, security, and business-support services. These perceptions increase confidence in the economic environment, enhance business planning, and foster growth-oriented decision-making.

Trust in Government and Organisational Performance: The study revealed a positive and significant relationship between trust in government and organizational performance

(growth and operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria. The findings of the study concur with the research carried out by Oloruntoaba (2021) in Oyo State, Nigeria, that trust in government has a statistically significant, positive effect on voluntary tax compliance. This finding suggests that MSMEs thrive in environments where public institutions are viewed as credible, competent, and accountable. Trust encourages cooperation with regulatory bodies, reduces uncertainty, and enhances the social contract between taxpayers and government. When MSMEs believe that government policies are stable and supportive, they are more likely to invest, expand operations, and innovate.

Conclusion, Policy Implications, Limitations and Further Research

The link between behavioural taxation and the organizational performance of MSMEs in Nigeria reveals that taxation is not only an economic or regulatory issue but also a behavioural and psychological one. Evidence from the empirical analysis shows that behavioural factors such as tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government significantly shape how MSMEs respond to tax obligations. These behavioural elements, in turn, influence compliance levels, financial reporting practices, resource allocation, and ultimately business performance. Overall, the findings suggest that positive behavioural taxation factors tend to enhance organizational performance. For

instance, high tax morale and a fair tax system improve voluntary compliance, reduce the cost and risk of penalties, and support formalisation conditions that assist MSMEs in gaining access to credit, government support, and broader markets. In essence, the relationship between behavioural taxation and MSMEs' performance in Nigeria is conditional: behavioural factors matter greatly, but their impact depends on the fairness, simplicity, and transparency of the tax structure. Therefore, the conclusion is that behavioural taxation plays a substantial role in shaping MSMEs organizational performance in Nigeria. A supportive tax environment, one perceived as fair, transparent, and efficient, allows positive taxpayer behaviours to translate into improved performance. This highlights the need for an integrated policy approach that combines behavioural insights with broad-based tax system reforms to fully harness the role of taxation in advancing MSMEs performance.

The finding of a positive and significant link between behavioural taxation (tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government) and organizational performance (growth and operational performance) of MSMEs in Nigeria has vital policy implications for tax authorities, government institutions, and business support agencies. Since behavioural factors such as tax morale, procedural fairness, distributive fairness and trust in government shape tax compliance and influence business outcomes,

policy interventions must target these behavioural dimensions alongside structural tax reforms. First, a key implication is the need for government accountability and transparency. MSMEs are more willing to comply when they trust that tax revenues are used responsibly. Therefore, the government should strengthen anti-corruption policies and ensure visible accountability in public spending. Secondly, the government should eliminate multiple and overlapping taxes imposed by federal, state, and local authorities. Also, strengthen dispute resolution mechanisms so MSMEs feel protected from unfair assessment. Thirdly, tax knowledge plays a vital behavioural role. Many MSMEs do not comply due to misunderstanding or lack of awareness, rather than deliberate evasion. Hence, government agencies such as the Nigerian Revenue Service (NRS) should continuously design tax education programmes. Fourth, positive behavioural engagements with tax officials improve compliance and reduce fear or hostility. Hence, policies should introduce taxpayer service desks and digital help platforms for prompt assistance. Fifth, since behavioural taxation improves performance, MSMEs targeted incentives should be designed to reinforce positive behaviour, such as grants, loans, and support programmes tied to demonstrated tax responsibility.

Despite providing significant contributions to literature, this study has several limitations. The study primarily relied on MSMEs within selected region of Nigeria, which may not fully

represent the diversity of business sectors, cultural context, or regional tax practices across the country. Consequently, the findings may have limited generalizability to all Nigerian MSMEs. Secondly, the study employed a cross-sectional research design, capturing data at a single point in time. This limits the ability to establish a causal link between behavioural taxation and organizational performance. Thirdly, much of the data on tax behaviour and organizational performance were self-reported by respondents. This introduces the potential for response bias, including social desirability bias, as MSME owners may overstate compliance or underreport challenges. Fourth, behavioural taxation encompasses psychological, social, and moral factors such as trust, moral and fairness. While the study employed validated measurement scales, these constructs are inherently subjective, and their quantification may not fully capture the complexity of behavioural motivations. Fifth, factors such as macroeconomic conditions, access to finance, infrastructure, or sector specific regulations can influence MSMEs performance independently of behavioural taxation. These dimensions were not comprehensively controlled in this study, which may affect the precision of the observed correlation.

To build on current research and address its limitations, future studies could consider the following directions:

1. Future research should adopt longitudinal designs to track changes in behavioural taxation and MSMEs performance over time. This would help establish causal link and capture the dynamic effects of policy changes and behavioural interventions.
2. Expanding the study to include MSMEs from multiple regions, sectors, and informal enterprises would improve the representativeness of findings and allow for comparative analysis between regions and industries.
3. Integrating qualitative methods such as interviews, focus groups, or case studies can

References

AbdelNabi, M., Afraz, N., Ahmed, T., Ayub, A., Makki, F., Said, F., Schiekltekat, P., & Vlaev, I. (2024). Nudging tax filling through text message combinations; Evidence from Pakistan. *Behavioural Public Policy*, 1 – 22. <https://doi.org/10.107/bpp.2024.61>

Abdullahi, S. K., Shittu, I. O., & Lawan, Y. (2025). Effect of multiple taxation system on the growth of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *IRE Journals*, 9(3), 1197 – 1208.

Abubakar, A., & Baba, B. U. (2024). Assessing the behaviour intention of informal small and medium scale businesses towards payment of presumptive tax in Nigeria. *International Journal of Intellectual Discourse*, 7(4). Retrieved from

provide deeper insights into the motivations, perceptions, and challenges of MSME owners, complementing quantitative findings.

4. Future research should consider the role of macroeconomic indicators, regulatory frameworks, and financial access as moderating or mediating variables in the association between behavioural taxation and MSME performance.
5. Investigating specific sectors may show variations in behavioural taxation effects given that different industries face distinct regulatory and market conditions.

<https://ijidjournal.org/index.php/ijid/article/view/681>

Adebayo, O. A., Okoye, C. I., & Ibrahim, Y. (2024). Organizational performance and internal control systems: Evidence from Nigerian SMEs. *Current Journal of Human Resources Management*, 10(4), 19 – 31.

Adedeji, A., & Lawal, A. (2024). Tax morale and compliance behaviour among SMEs in South-West Nigeria. *Journal of Tax Administration and Economics*, 6(1), 32 – 48.

Adeniran, T., & Olayinka, O. (2023). Tax policy and SMEs performance in Nigeria: Mediating role of compliance behaviour. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation Studies*, 15(2), 45 – 60.

Agbetunde, L. A., Akinrinola, O. O., & Anyahara, I. O. (2020). A survey of religiosity, tax morale and compliance among micro, small and medium-scale enterprises in Nigeria. *Journal of Taxation and Economic Development*, 19(1), 35 – 49.

Agbi, N., Bagshaw, K. B., & Lebura, S. (2024). Stakeholder engagement and operational performance of construction firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Management Research*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.5296/jmr.v15i2.21328>

Ajibola, A. B., & Lateef, S. A. (2023). Determinants of tax compliance in Nigeria: An insight into Federal Inland Revenue Service. *Kashere Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(1). <https://kajaf.com.ng/index.php/kajaf/article/view/30/23>

Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour,. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179 – 211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)

Ajzen, I. (2015). The theory of planned behaviour: Frequently asked questions. <https://people.unmass.edu/ajzen/pdf/tpb.questions.pdf>

Akinyemi, K., & Adewale, S. (2023). Multiple taxation and the growth of small enterprises in Lagos State. *International*

Journal of Business and Management Review, 11(4), 101 – 115.

Alabi, A. W., Atanda, F. A., Akintoye, I. R., & Kajola, S. G. (2024). Tax morale and taxpayers' compliance among SMEs in Nigeria. *Journal of Management World*, 2(2), 68 –78. <https://doi.org/10.53935/jomw.v2024i2.278>

Alawode, O., & Adegbe, F. F. (2022). Taxpayers' behaviour and tax compliance outcomes: Function of tax justice in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 91 – 115.

Al-Mujtaba, A. (2021). Multiple taxation is killing Nigerian SMEs. SME Conference and Exhibition Organized by the Abuja Chamber of Commerce and Industry. July 20-21.

Alm, J., & Kasper, M. (2023). Using behavioural economics to understand tax compliance. *Economics & Political Studies*, 11(3), 279 – 294.

Anaba, C., & Oboh, M. (2021). Tax culture and informal business performance in Nigeria. *African Journal of Economics and Policy*, 8(3), 88 – 102.

Appah, E. & Duoduo, G. (2023a). Tax determinants and sustainable economic

- growth of MSMEs in South–South, Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 11(4), 15 – 46.
- Appah, E. and Duoduo, G. (2023b). Determinants of tax Compliance behaviour and sustainable economic growth among MSMEs in Nigeria, *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 11(3), 70-105.
- Atawodi, o., & Ojeka, S.A. (2012). Factors that affect tax compliance among SMEs in North Central Nigeria. *International Journal of Business Management*, 7(12), 87 – 96.
- Bani-Khalid, D., Alshira'h, I., & Alshirah, I. (2022). Determinants of tax compliance intention among Jordanian SMEs: A focus on the theory of planned behaviour. *Economics*, 10(2). <https://dou.org/10.3390/economics10020030>
- Biswakarma, G., & Bohora, B. (2025). Dynamic capabilities and organizational performance: The mediating role of organizational resilience in IT sector. *Future Business Journal*, 11, Article 173. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-025-00592-w>
- Cummings, R. G., Martinez-Vazquez, J., & Torgler, B. (2022). Tax compliance and trust: New evidence from developing countries. *Public Finance Review*, 50(2), 187 – 210.
- Cuntu, E. G. (2020). Organisational performance – theoretical and practical approaches, study on students' perceptions. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*, 14(1), 398 – 406. <https://doi.org/10.2478/picbe-2020-0038>
- David, F. O., & Bello, A. O. (2025). Taxpayers' awareness, perception, and compliance in the informal sector within Oyo North, Nigeria. *Science Journal of Business and Management*, 13(3), 187 195.
- Doyle, E. (2022). Encouraging ethical tax compliance behaviour: The role of tax practitioner in enhancing tax justice. *Law and Contemporary Problems*, 85(4), 136 – 155
- Elbadawy, G. A., Amr, M., & Hamed, M. (2024). The effect of organizational agility on organizational performance. *Journal of Advances in Economics and Business Studies*, 19(1), 1 – 28.
- Ellawule, A., Bashir, Y. M., Dalhat, B. S. & Suleiman, N. (2024). Moderating effect of tax knowledge on the relationship between tax rates and tax compliance of MSMEs in

- Nigeria. *FUDMA Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 2(1), 118 – 133.
- Etang, C. O., Numaliya, P. F., Antuwa, G. D., & Richards, A. O. (2025). Evaluating the impact of multiple taxation on the financial performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *SSR Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 2(8), 1 – 13.
- Enang, E. R., Alexander, J.O. & Faleye, O. J. (2022). The influence of taxation on the performance of SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 13(2), 01 – 12.
- Eze, P., & Umeji, F. (2022). Tax fairness and MSMEs sustainability in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Research*, 14(1), 59 – 74.
- Ezinwa, v., & Nwosu, C. (2022). Tax perception, fairness and compliance among small businesses in Nigeria. *African Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 9(2), 22 – 36.
- Feld, L. P. & Frey, B. (2007). Tax compliance as the result of a psychological tax context: The role of incentives and responsive regulation. *Law and Policy*, 29(1), 102 – 120. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9930.2007>
- Gimba, H. Y., & Ibrahim, I. (2017). SMEs view on the theory of planned behaviour and penalty magnitude: Preliminary findings from Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 3(1), 39 – 50. <https://doi.org/10.26710/ijsee.v3i1.180>
- Gunel, T. & Didinmez, I. (2023). Relationship between rule of law and tax revenue: Dynamic panel data analysis. *Public Sector Economics*, 46(3), 403 – 418.
- Hauptman, L., Zmuk, B., & Decman, N. (2024). Tax governance in compliance: The role of motivational postures and behavioural intentions. *Business Perspectives*, 22(1), 500 – 513.
- Ijeoma, O. T. (2021). An empirical analysis of firm growth and financial performance of selected firms in Nigeria. *African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research*, 4(3), 150 – 161
- Ikidi, P.-G., Akhimie, E. O. & Ozuah, O. L. (2024). Tax morale, governance quality and tax compliance in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 15(5,se.4), 24 – 35.
- Inim, V. E., Udoh, F. S., & Ede, U. S. (2020). Taxation and the growth of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria (2007 – 2019). *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 7(3), 229 – 235. <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.500.2020.73.229.235>

- Ilodigwe, A. O. (2023). The impact of multiple taxation on the efficiency of selected SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Global Online Journal of Academic Research (GOJAR)*. <https://www.nigeriajournalonline.com/index.php/GOJAR/article/view/3947>
- Kimotho, M., & Kariuki, J. (2024). Organisational performance: A comprehensive measure of resource use, value delivery and competitiveness, *International Journal of Social Sciences, Management and Entrepreneurship*, 8(3), 723 – 737.
- Kirchler, E., Hoelzl, E., & Wahl, I. (2008). Enforced versus voluntary tax compliance
- Kirchler, E. (2007). *The Economic Psychology of Tax Behaviour*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kristy, B. F., Baridwan, Z., & Rusydi, M. K. (2022). Determinants of tax compliance for business actors and independent workers in the perspective of theory of planned behaviour and theory of fiscal psychology. *International Journal of Accounting & Business Society*, 30(2). <https://doi.org/10.21776/ijabs.2022.30.2.668>
- Lawal, L. O., Hashidu, S. M., Lawal, T., & Muftah, S. A. (2025). Effect of socio-psychological factors on voluntary tax compliance in Gombe State. *Journal of the Management Sciences*, 61(8), 269 – 283.
- Lucky, M., Baridoo, F., & Leyira, M. C. (2025). Deterrence and tax morale: The moderating effect of corruption in Nigeria. *GPH – International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 8(9), 01 – 11.
- Nwanne, D. C., Basse, E. O., Amoke, C. V., Anakwue, E. C., & Essien, O. E. (2023). Infrastructures, taxation and performance of micro and small enterprises in Nigeria. *ISRG Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 1(11), 18 – 25.
- Ofoegbu, W. C., & Efeh, V. O. (2023). Lean production and operational performance of manufacturing firms in Rivers State. *GPH-International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 5(12), 30 – 43. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514893>
- Ofurn, C. D., & Obi, H. K. (2023). Firm growth determinants and sustainable growth of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance*, 8(11), 1 – 15.
- Ojo, A. O., & Shittu, S. A. (2023). Value added tax compliance and small and medium enterprises in Nigeria: Analysis of influential factors. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(2), 2228553.

- Okafor, G., Ojo, T., & Balogun, L. (2021). Tax complexity and SME performance in Nigeria. *Journal of African Business Studies*, 17(2), 75 – 89. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264268920.en>
- Oloruntoba, O. (2021). Trust in government, peer group influence and voluntary tax compliance among small and medium enterprises owners in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Kashere Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(1), 129 – 153.
- Oloyede, A. M., Otusanya, O. J. & Ala-Peters, D. (2022). Taxation and the performance of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Accounting*,
- Olumoh, Y. A. (2024). Strategic management controls and operational performance of small and medium enterprises in South - West Nigeria. *Malete Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 4(2), 176 – 190. <https://doi.org/10.6658d2f4da4fe09d5b611bcf40cf3>
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2023). Tax policy reforms 2023: OECD and selected partner economies. <https://doi.org/10.1787/74edb7c3-en>
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). (2017). Trust and public policy: How better government can help rebuild public trust. OECD Publishing.
- Orishede, F. (2024). Building blocks and organizational performance. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences*. 3(1). Doi:10.47772/ijriss.2023.7012151
- Olotuntoba, O. (2021). Trust in government, peer group influence and voluntary tax compliance among small and medium enterprises owners in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Kashere Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(1), 129 – 153. <https://www.kajaf.com.ng/index.php/kajaf/article/view/12>
- Oporiopo, M.G. & Tamarauebi, O.C. (2021). Multiplicity of taxation in Nigeria and its controversy. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*. 9(2), 1-12
- Oseifuah, E. (2025). Augmented theory of planned behaviour, tax literacy and tax compliance in developing countries: A conceptual framework. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(3), 369 – 378. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v.14i3.3823>
- Osim, E. O., Daferighe, E. E., & Ukpong, M.O. (2020). Financial reporting practices and sustainability of micro, small and medium

- enterprises (MSMEs) in Akwa Ibom State. *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 3(12), 920 – 940.
- Oyedele, P., Alao, M., & Ifayemi, O. (2025). Tax justice, tax administration and tax compliance of small and medium enterprises in Lagos State. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 10(1), 72 – 85. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijafm.20251001.15>
- Oyeniya, O. C., & Okoughenu, S. A. (2023). Tax justice and voluntary compliance of the taxpayers in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Business Management and Accounting*, (IJEEMA), 3(2), 87 – 96. <https://doi.org/10.59890/ijebma.v.3i2.451>
- Rexhepi, B., & Berisha, O. R. (2025). Organisational performance and strategic management. *Transnational Academic Journal of Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10884187>
- SMEDAN (2022). *National Survey of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)*. Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria, Abuja.
- Shaharruddin, N. S., Palil, M. R., Ramli, R., & Maelah, R. (2023). Understanding tax compliance among sole proprietors: A theory of planned behaviour analysis. *Journal of Management and Muamalah*, 13(2), 114 – 126. <https://doi.org/10.53840/jmm.v13i2.178>
- Torgler, B. (2007). Tax compliance and tax morale: A theoretical and empirical analysis. *Edward Elgar Publishing*.
- Udeh, F. N. P., Odion, A., & Izevbekhai, M. O. (2022). Effect of multiple taxation on the growth of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Science and Management*, 2(5), 120 – 142.
- Udo, A., & Nnaji, P. (2023). Behavioural taxation and MSME performance: A conceptual review. *Journal of Business and Economic Behavior*, 9(3), 55 – 69.
- Umukoro, S. & Onou, D. F. (2024). Multiple taxation and the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria: A literature review. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship, Technology and Innovation*, 1(1), 151 – 161.
- Vincent, O. (2021). Assessing SMEs tax non-compliance behaviour in Sub-Saharan Africa: An insight from Nigeria. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2021.1938930>

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Weber, T. O., Fookan, J., & Herrmann, B. (2014). Behavioural economics and taxation (Taxation Paper No. 14). Directorate – General for Taxation and Customs Union, European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2778/32009>

Wenzel, M. (2003). Tax compliance and the psychology of justice: Mapping the field. In V. Braithwaite (Ed.), *Taxing democracy: Understanding tax avoidance and evasion* (pp. 41 – 69). Ashgate.